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Anowar's Handbook on Materials Engineering and Practices

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Key note of handwritten book

This preprint book is helpful for material engineers/scientists, textile engineers, students, researchers, professors and professionals in the field *Engineering Materials and Practices*. This handbook is written from author's notebook for exam preparation in Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering.

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ME-201, Engineering materials and practices

course instructor: zulfar Ferdous

Stress:

$$\text{Stress, } \sigma = \frac{F}{A}$$

Normal stress: load is applied perpendicular direction of the area i.e called normal stress.

Shear stress: load is applied parallel direction of the area.

Tensile: when tension is occurred.

compressive: when compression is occurred.

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*** Draw the stress-strain curve?

*** Hook's law:

$\text{stress} \propto \text{strain}$

*** Write down the components of internal effects on exploratory section a-a.

Fig: components of internal effects on exploratory section

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$P_{xx} \rightarrow$ Axial force. This component measures the pulling (or, pushing) action perpendicular to the section. A pull represents a tensile force that tends to elongate the member, whereas a push is a compressive force that tends to shorten it. It is often denoted by p .

$P_{xy}, P_{xz} \rightarrow$ Shear forces. These components of the total resistance to sliding the portion to one side of the exploratory section past the other. The resultant shear force is usually designated by v , and its components by v_y and v_z to identify their directions.

$M_{xx} \rightarrow$ Torque. This component measures the resistance to twisting the member and is commonly given the symbol T .

$M_{xy}, M_{xz} \rightarrow$ Bending moments. These components measure the resistance to bending the member about the y or z axes and are often denoted merely by M_y or M_z .

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Prob#01 A composite bar consists of an aluminium section rigid by fastened between a bronze section and a steel section, as shown in the figure. Axial loads are applied at the positions indicated. Determine the stress in each section.

Ans:

$$\sigma = \frac{P}{A} \rightarrow \text{Formula}$$

$$\sigma_{br} = \frac{4000}{1.2} = 3330 \text{ psi (Tension)}$$

$$\sigma_{Al} = \frac{5000}{1.8} = 2780 \text{ psi (compression)}$$

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$$G_{st} = \frac{7000}{16} = 4375 \text{ psi (compression)}$$

Prob# 02 : For the truss shown down, determine the stress in members AC and BD. The cross sectional area of each member is 900 mm^2 .

4 panels at 4m = 16m

$$\begin{aligned} \uparrow \sum F_y = 0 & \quad A_y - 30 - 70 + H_y \\ & \quad (A_y + H_y) = 100 \\ \rightarrow \sum M_H = 0 & \quad -A_y \times 16 + 30 \times 12 + 70 \times 4 = 0 \\ & \Rightarrow A_y = \frac{640}{16} = 40 \text{ kN} \\ & \quad H_y = 60 \text{ kN} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sum F_x = 0 & \quad H_x = 0 \\ \sum M = 0 & \quad \begin{array}{r} 360 \\ 280 \\ \hline 640 \end{array} \end{aligned}$$

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$$\frac{F_{AB}}{5} = \frac{F_{Ax}}{4} = \frac{40}{3}$$

$$F_{Ax} = \frac{40 \times 4}{3} = 53.33 \text{ kN}$$

$$\sigma_{Ax} = \frac{F_{Ax}}{A} = \frac{53.33 \times 10^3}{900 \times 10^{-6}}$$

$$= 59.26 \times 10^6 \text{ Pa}$$

$$= 59.26 \text{ MPa} \text{ Ans.}$$

Again,

$$\frac{F_{DE}}{5} = \frac{F_{BD}}{4} = \frac{30}{3}$$

$$\therefore F_{BD} = 40 \text{ kN}$$

$$\sigma_{BD} = \frac{40 \times 10^3}{900 \times 10^{-6}} = 44.4 \times 10^6 \text{ Pa}$$

$$= 44.4 \text{ MPa} \text{ Ans.}$$

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Prob # 03: The block of weight w hangs from the pin at A .
The bars AB and AC are pinned to the support at B and C . The
areas are 800 mm^2 for AB and 400 mm^2 for AC . Neglecting
the weights of the bars, determine the maximum safe value of
 w if the stress in AB is limited to 110 MPa and that in AC to
 120 MPa .

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Here,

$$\sum F_x = 0$$
$$P_{AC} \cos 60^\circ - P_{AB} \cos 40^\circ = 0$$
$$\Rightarrow P_{AC} \cos 60^\circ = P_{AB} \cos 40^\circ$$
$$\Rightarrow P_{AC} = 1.53 P_{AB}$$

$$\oplus \uparrow \sum F_y = 0$$
$$P_{AC} \sin 60^\circ + P_{AB} \sin 40^\circ - W = 0$$
$$\Rightarrow 1.53 P_{AB} + P_{AB} \sin 40^\circ - W = 0$$
$$\therefore P_{AB} = \frac{W}{1.53 + \sin 40^\circ}$$
$$P_{AC} = 1.53 \times P_{AB}$$
$$AB/C = \frac{P_{AB}}{A}$$
$$\Rightarrow P_{AB} = GA = 120 \times 10^6 \times 800 \times 10^{-6}$$

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$$P_{Ac} = 6A$$
$$= 116 \times 10^6 \times 400 \times 10^{-6}$$

Maximum safe value should be the lower value of w . Because for higher value of w can break down the safe value.

Ques:

Find out the value of P_{BC}

F_{AB} and (a) $\sigma_{BC} = 2$

(b) Dia of BC = 20 mm

(b) If stress in BC is limited to 100 MPa

what should be the dia of bar BC.

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*** what do you understand by strain ?

Ans:

Strain is the ratio of the change in length to the original length.

Let,

Original length = L

After applied the tensile force P ,

Elongation will be S

$$\therefore \epsilon = \frac{S}{L}$$

*** Draw the stress-strain diagram and discuss it:

Fig: stress-strain curve for ductile material

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Geometrical part plane computer: perforated & wide
where
A = Proportional limit
B = Elastic limit
C = Yield point
D = Ultimate strength
E = Rupture strength.

The data obtained from the tension test are generally plotted as a stress-strain diagram.

- ✓ The initial linear portion of the curve OA is the elastic region. point A is the elastic limit, defined as the greatest stress that the metal can withstand with^{out} experiencing a permanent strain. When the load is removed. The determination of elastic limit is quite tedious. (No often replaced by proportional limit B.
- ✓ The proportional limit is the stress at which the stress-strain curve deviates from linearity.
- For engineering purposes, the limit of usable elastic behaviour is described by yield strength, point C.
- ✓ The yield strength is defined as the stress which will produce a small amount of permanent strain.

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Plastic deformation begins when the elastic limit is exceeded. As the plastic deformation of the specimen increases the metal becomes stronger so that the load required to extend the specimen increases with further straining. Eventually the load reaches a maximum value. The maximum load divided by the area of the specimen is the ultimate strength. For a ductile material the diameter of the specimen begins to decrease rapidly beyond maximum load. So that the load required to continue deformation drops off until the specimen fractures.

*** Discuss about ductile vs brittle behaviour?

Ans: The general behaviour of material under load can be classified as ductile or brittle depending upon whether the metal is able to undergo plastic deformation.

A completely brittle material would fracture almost at the elastic limit, whereas ductility allows the material to redistribute localized stresses. In brittle materials, localized stresses continue to

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A crack slowly propagates in an individual component
build up, finally a crack forms at one or more points
of stress concentration and it spreads rapidly over
the section.

Brittleness is not an absolute property of a material.

A metal such as: tungsten, which is brittle at room temp.
is ductile at an elevated temp. A metal which is brittle
in tension may be ductile under hydrostatic compression.
Furthermore, a metal which is ductile in tension at
room temp. can become brittle in the presence of notches,
low temp. high rates of loading etc.

*** Discuss about Hooke's law of Elasticity?

Ans: Hooke's law states:
stress is proportional to strain.

Mathematically,

$$\sigma \propto \epsilon$$
$$\Rightarrow \sigma = E \epsilon$$

where, $E \rightarrow$ modulus of Elasticity.

$$\Rightarrow \frac{P}{A} = E \cdot \frac{\delta}{L}$$
$$\therefore \delta = \frac{PL}{AE}$$

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Assumptions:

1. The load must be axial
2. The bar have a const. x-section and be homogeneous.
3. The stress must not exceed the proportional limit.

in order to prove the given data. To know shearing strain, $\delta = \frac{\delta_s}{L}$

According to Hook's law for shearing stress,

$$\tau = G \delta$$

where, $G = \text{modulus of rigidity.}$

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*** Write short notes on Poisson's ratio:

Ans: If a bar is lengthened by axial tension then there is a reduction in transverse dimension.

The ratio of the unit deformations or strains in these directions is const, for stresses within the proportional limit.

Mathematically,

Poisson's ratio,

$$\nu = -\frac{\epsilon_y}{\epsilon_x}$$

$$\epsilon_z = -\frac{\epsilon_x}{\nu}$$

$$\Rightarrow \epsilon_x = -\frac{\epsilon_z}{\nu}$$

$$\epsilon_x = \frac{1}{E} \{ \sigma_x - \nu (\sigma_y + \sigma_z) \}$$

$$\epsilon_y = \frac{1}{E} \{ \sigma_y - \nu (\sigma_x + \sigma_z) \}$$

$$\epsilon_z = \frac{1}{E} \{ \sigma_z - \nu (\sigma_x + \sigma_y) \}$$

Relation between G , E and ν

$$G = \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)}$$

where,

G = Modulus of rigidity

E = Modulus of Elasticity

ν = Poisson's ratio.

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Principle: of failure analysis **Failure Analysis:**

had consideration. Disruptors and concerns
In any failure analysis it is important to get
as much information as possible from the failed
part itself along with an investigation of the conditions
at the time of failure.

In following questions to be asked are:

- (i) How long was the part in service?
- (ii) What was the nature of stresses at the time of failure?
- (iii) What was the part subjected to an overload?
- (iv) Was the part properly installed?
- (v) Were there any changes in the environment?
- (vi) Was the part properly maintained?

write down the types of loading?
In many cases, the type of load is a contributing
factor to failure. There are essentially five types of loads:

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Q. Write down the classification of failure causes?

Ans:

1. Failure due to faulty processing

(a) Flaws due to faulty composition
(b) Defects originating in ingot making or casting
(c) Irregularities due to machining, grinding etc.
(d) Defects due to welding (Porosity, undercut, cracks etc)
(e) Flaws due to case hardening.
(f) Defects due to surface treatments.

2. Failure due to faulty design:

(a) Ductile failure
(b) Brittle fracture
(c) Fatigue failure

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(4) High temperature failure
(creep, oxidation, local melting etc.)

(e) static delayed fracture

(f) Excessively severe stress raisers inherent
in the design.

(g) Inadequate stress analysis.
(অপর্যাপ্ত)

(3) Failure due to deterioration during service condition:

(a) Over load

(b) Wear

(c) Corrosion

(d) In adequate maintenance/ improper repair

(e) Disintegration due to chemical attack

(f) Radiation damage.

(g) Accidental conditions.

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Strain Energy

*** What do you understand by strain energy?

Whenever some load is applied it extends and loses its potential energy. This energy is absorbed by the elongated member which may be released by removing the load. This energy which is absorbed in a body, when strained within its elastic limit is known as strain energy.

Mathematically,

$$\text{Strain energy} = \text{Work done.}$$

The term resilience is used for the total strain energy stored in a body. Some-time resilience is also defined as the capacity of a strained body for doing work on the removal of the straining force.

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*** What do you understand by proof resilience?

Ans: It is a common term used for maximum resilience and may be defined as the maximum strain energy which can be stored in a body. (This happens when the body is stressed up to elastic limit.)

*** What do you understand by Modulus of resilience?

Ans: The proof resilience per unit volume of a material is known as modulus of resilience.

*** Write down the types of Loading.

Ans: → Gradually

→ Suddenly

→ with impact.

Strain energy stored in a body for gradually applied loading :

It is the most common and practical way of loading a body, in which the loading starts from

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zero and increases gradually till the body is fully loaded.

Now, consider a metallic bar subjected to gradual loading.

Let,

P = load gradually applied

A = cross sectional area of the bar

L = length of the bar

E = Modulus of Elasticity

δ = Deformation of the bar due to Load.

Since the load applied is gradual and varies from zero to P .

So average load is $P/2$

Work done = Force x distance

= Avg. load x Deformation

$P/2 \times \delta$

$\frac{1}{2} \sigma \epsilon AL$
 $= \frac{1}{2} \text{Stress} \times \text{Strain} \times \text{Volume}$

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1.
$$= \frac{1}{2} \times \sigma \times \frac{\sigma}{E} \times AL$$

$$= \frac{\sigma^2}{2E} \times AL$$

$$= \frac{\sigma^2}{2E} \times V$$

Since the energy stored is equal to the work done, No strain energy stored,

$$U = \frac{\sigma^2}{2E} \times V$$

Modulus of resilience = strain energy per unit volume

$$= \frac{\sigma^2}{2E}$$

Prob#

Calculate the strain energy stored in a bar of 2m long, 50mm wide and 40mm thick when it is subjected to a tensile load of 60kN. $E = 6 \text{ GPa}$, 200 GPa

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But you would have strain energy stored in a body when load is suddenly applied.

let, $P =$ Load applied suddenly

$A =$ sectional area of the bar.

$L =$ length of the bar.

$E =$ Modulus of elasticity of the material.

$\delta =$ Deformation of the bar
 $\sigma =$ stress induced by the load suddenly applied.

Since the load is applied suddenly so the load (P) is constant throughout the process of the deformation of the bar.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Work done} &= \text{force} \times \text{distance} \\ &= \text{Load} \times \text{deformation} \\ &= P \times \delta \end{aligned}$$

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We know strain energy stored,

$$U = \frac{a^2}{2E} \times V$$

Since the energy stored is equal to the work done

$$P \times \delta = \frac{a^2}{2E} \times V$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{a^2}{2E} \times A \times L = P \times \frac{a \times L}{E}$$

$$\Rightarrow a = 2 \times \frac{P}{A} \times \frac{V}{L}$$

$$a = E \epsilon$$

$$a = E \cdot \frac{\delta}{L}$$

$$\delta = \frac{a \times L}{E}$$

So, the stress induced in this case is twice the stress induced when the same load is applied gradually.

Prob# An axial pull of 20kN is suddenly applied on a steel rod of 2.5m long and 1000mm² in x-section. Calculate the strain energy, which can be absorbed in the rod, E = 200 GPa.

Given, $A = 1000 \text{ mm}^2 = 1000 \text{ mm}^2$

$$P = 20 \text{ kN} = 20 \times 10^3$$

$$V = A L$$

$$= 1 \times 2.5 \text{ m}^3$$

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Prob # A steel rod of 28 mm diameter is 2.5 m long. Find the maximum instantaneous strain and work done at maximum elongation, when an axial load of 50 kN is suddenly applied to it. Also calculate the maximum dynamic force in the rod. $E = 200 \text{ GPa}$.

Here,

$$\text{Diameter} = 28 \text{ mm} = 28 \text{ m} \times 10^{-3}$$

$$A = \frac{\pi d^2}{4} = \frac{\pi \times (28)^2 \times (10^{-3})^2}{4} = 6.15 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2$$

$$l = 2.5 \text{ m}$$

$$P = 50 \times 10^3 \text{ N}$$

$$V = Al =$$

$$\sigma_{max} = \frac{2P}{A} = \frac{50 \times 10^3}{6.15 \times 10^{-4}} = 1.62 \times 10^8 \text{ N/m}^2$$

$$\delta = \frac{\sigma}{2E} \times l$$

$$\delta = \sigma \times \frac{l}{E}$$

$$= 1.62 \times 10^8 \times \frac{2.5}{200 \times 10^9}$$

$$= 2.03 \text{ mm}$$

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$$W = \rho \times V = \rho \times A \times L$$

$$= 50 \times 10^3 \times 2.03 \times 10^{-3}$$

And maximum dynamic force

$$= A \times \sigma$$

$$= 6.15 \times 10^{-4} \times 1.62 \times 10^8$$

Strain Energy stored in a body of varying section:

Total strain Energy, $U = U_1 + U_2 + U_3$

Prob# A non-uniform tension bar of 1m long is made up of 2 parts as shown in the figure:

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(i) Find the total strain energy stored in the bar when it is subjected to a gradual load of 70 kN.

(ii) Find the total strain energy stored in the bar when it is made of uniform cross-section of the same volume. $E = 200 \text{ GPa}$.

Ans:

$$\sigma_1 = \frac{P}{A_1} = \frac{70 \times 10^3}{1000 \times 10^{-6}}$$

$$V_1 = A_1 \times l_1 = (1000 \times 10^{-6})(3)$$

$$U_1 = \frac{\sigma_1^2}{2E} \times V_1 = \dots$$

Like wise,

$$\sigma_2 = \frac{P}{A_2} = \frac{70 \times 10^3}{2000 \times 10^{-6}}$$

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The f. $v_2 = A_2 \times J_2$

$v_2 = (2000 \times 10^{-6}) \times 2$

The f. $u_2 = \frac{\sigma_2}{2E} \times v_2$

Condition will be held in case of

$u = u_1 + u_2$

$v = v_1 + v_2$

X-Section Total area,

Volume of the bar = $\frac{\text{Volume of the bar}}{\text{Length of the bar}}$

$A = \frac{7 \times 10^6 \text{ mm}^3}{5 \times 10^3 \text{ m}}$

So $\sigma = \frac{P}{A} = 70 \times 10^3$

$U = \frac{\sigma}{2E} \times V$

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*** What do you understand by Alloy? (সংকর)

Ans: A substance having metallic properties and being composed of two or more chemical elements of which at least one is an elemental metal.

Alloying element:

An element which is added to a metal to effect changes in properties and which remains within the metal.

Alloy steel: steel containing significant amount of alloying elements (other than carbon) added to effect changes in the mechanical or physical properties.

Metallic materials may be divided into two groups.

(a) Ferrous (Iron-based)

(b) Non ferrous (other than iron like)

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Copper, aluminium, magnesium, nickel, tin, lead, zinc etc)

Purpose of alloying:

1. Increase hardenability
2. Improve strength of ordinary temp.
3. Improve mechanical properties either at high or low temp.
4. Improve toughness.
5. Increase wear resistance.
6. Increase corrosion resistance.
7. Improve magnetic properties.

*** What do you understand by copper and copper alloys?

Ans: The important properties of copper are high electrical and thermal conductivity, good corrosion resistance, machinability, strength and ease of fabrication. In addition, copper is nonmagnetic, having pleasant color, can be welded, brazed and soldered and is easily finished by plating.

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Certain of these basic properties may be improved
now by suitable alloying. Head: Dab Reference

Copper alloys: The most important commercial
copper alloys may be classified as follows:

1. Brasses: Alloys of copper and zinc
 - A. Alpha brasses - (containing upto 36% zinc)
 - (1) Yellow alpha brasses → 20-36% zinc
 - (2) Red brasses - 5-20% zinc
 - B. Alpha plus — (3) Beta brasses (54-62% copper)
2. Bronzes - upto 12% of alloying elements
 - A. Tin Bronzes
 - B. Silicon Bronzes
 - (3) Aluminium Bronzes
 - A) Beryllium.

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3. Cupronickel - Alloy of copper and nickel

4. Nickel silver - Alloy of copper, nickel and zinc

Discuss about aluminium and aluminium alloys?

Ans: The best known characteristics of aluminium is its light weight, good malleability and formability, high corrosion resistance, high electrical and thermal conductivity. An ultra pure form of aluminium is used for photographic reflectors.

Aluminium is non toxic, non magnetic and non sparking. The non negative characteristic makes aluminium useful for electrical shielding. The light weight properties makes it suitable for electrical conductor for many electrical applications.

Some aluminium alloys are -

- Aluminium copper alloy

- " " Manganese alloy

- " " Silicon "

- " " Magnesium "

- " " Silicon magnesium "

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*** what do you understand by Magnesium and Magnesium alloys?

Ans: The chief advantages of magnesium are its light weight, ease of machinability and high strength to weight ratio.

Because of its high chemical activity it finds use in the production of uranium and zirconium by thermal reduction with magnesium. Magnesium anodes

provide effective corrosion protection for water heaters, underground pipelines, ship hulls and ballast tanks.

Some magnesium alloys are

- Magnesium - Aluminium based alloys
- " - Zinc " "
- " - Thorium " "

*** Discuss briefly about Nickel and Nickel-alloys?

Ans: Nickel is characterized by good resistance to corrosion and oxidation. It is white in color.

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and has good mechanical properties. It forms tough, ductile alloys with many of the common metals. About 60% nickel produced is now used in stainless steel and nickel alloy steel. Because of its high corrosion resistance and hardness nickel makes an ideal coating for parts subjected to corrosion and wear.

Some Nickel alloys are-

- Nickel-copper based alloy
- " silicon-copper based alloy
- " chromium-iron " "
- " Molybdenum iron " "

*** Discuss briefly about lead and lead alloy?

Ans:

The major properties of lead include heavy weight, high density, softness, malleability, low melting point and low strength. It has lubricating properties, low electrical conductivity, high coefficient of expansion and high corrosion resistance.

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Some lead alloys are -
- Lead - Tin Antimony alloys
- Lead Antimony alloys
- lead - tin alloys.

Discuss briefly ferrous alloys?

Ans:

1. Nickel steel:

Nickel lowers the critical temp. of steels widens the temp. range, retards decomposition of austenite. It increases toughness, plasticity and fatigue strength.

Nickel steels are highly suited for high strength structural steels.

2. Chromium- steel:

Chromium is less expensive. These carbides have high hardness and good wear resistance, and high corrosion resistance.

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3. Nickel chromium steel:

In these steels the ratio of chromium to nickel is 1:2.5. The combined effect of nickel and chromium improves hardenability, wear resistance. They are used for worm gears, piston pin, aircraft gears, shafts, cams, automotive connecting rod, drive shaft etc.

4. Manganese steel:

Manganese is one of the least expensive alloying elements and is present in all steels as deoxidizer. Manganese also reduces the tendency towards hot-shortness resulting from the presence of sulfur thereby enabling the metal to be hot worked. Manganese sulfide has an outstanding in its power to combine with sulfur and manganese sulfide has a much higher melting point than iron sulfide. The manganese sulfide remains solid at the rolling temp and has a less adverse effect on the hot working properties of steel.

After a properly controlled heat treatment, this steel is characterized by high strength, high ductility and excellent resistance to wear.

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B. Molybdenum-steel:

Molybdenum is relatively expensive alloying element. Molybdenum has a strong effect on hardenability and increases the high temperature hardness and strength of steel. This element is most often used in combination with nickel and chromium or both nickel and chromium. It improves wear resistance and toughness.

The chromium molybdenum steels are relatively cheap and possess good hardening characteristics, ductility and weldability. They have been used extensively for pressure vessels, air craft structure parts, automobile axles and similar applications.

The nickel molybdenum steels have the advantages of the high strength and ductility from nickel, combined with deep hardening and improved machinability imparted by molybdenum. They have good toughness combined with high fatigue strength and wear resistance, used for gears, shafts, bearing etc.

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2 question }
Strain - ①
Strain - ①
Alloy - ②
Strain energy - ①
Failure Analysis - 1 question
Alloy - 1 question
Total → 4 question
Answer → 2 question

20.07.19
Time: 3:00

~~Q~~ What do you understand by fatigue?

Ans:

The phenomenon leading to fracture under repeated or fluctuating stresses having a maximum value less than the tensile strength of the material. Fatigue fractures are progressive, beginning as minute cracks that grow under the action of the fluctuating stress.

The number of cycles of stress that can be sustained prior to failure for a stated test condition is called fatigue life.

The maximum stress below which a material can endure an infinite number of stress cycles is the

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stress is not completely reversed, the value of the mean stress, minimum stress etc stress ratio should be stated.

✓ The minimum stress that can be sustained for a specified number of cycles without failure is called fatigue strength.

Why do a failure test?

In many applications materials are subjected to vibrating / oscillating forces. The behaviour of materials under such load conditions differ

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from the behaviour under a static load. Because the material is subjected to repeated load cycles in actual use, designers are forced to face with predicting fatigue life, which is defined as the total number of cycles to failure under specified loading conditions. Fatigue testing gives much better data to predict the in-service life of materials.

***** What do you understand by Hardness?**

Ans:

Resistance of metal to plastic deformation usually by indentation. However the term may also refer to stiffness or temper or to resistance to scratching, abrasion or cutting.

Hardness of a metal can be increased by suitable treatment; usually involving heating and cooling. When applicable the following more specific terms should be used

- Age hardening
- Case hardening
- Flame hardening
- Induction hardening

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Hardness is, however, used extensively to characterize materials and to determine whether they are suitable for their intended use.

Why use a hardness test

- Easy to perform
- quick 1 to 30 seconds.
- Relatively expensive
- Non destructive
- finished parts can be tested - but not ruined.
- Virtually any size and shape can be tested.

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*** what do you understand by hardness scale

Ans:

There are five major hardness scales

(i) Brinell - HB

(ii) Knoop - HK

(iii) Rockwell - HR

(iv) Shore - HS

(v) Vickers - HV

*** what do you understand by determining factors of hardness

Ans: There are five determining factors that can be used to determine the correct hardness that for different application -

(i) Material - grain size, metal, rubber etc.

(ii) Approximate hardness - hardened steel, rubber etc.

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iii. Shape - Thickness, size etc.

iv. Heat treatment - Annealing, quenching etc.

v. Production requirements.

*** What do you understand by toughness?

Ans: The ability of a metal to deform plastically and to absorb energy in the process before fracture is termed toughness.

Ductility is a measure of how much something deforms plastically before fracture, but just because a material is ductile does not make it tough, indeed toughness is a good combination of strength and ductility.

A material with high strength and high ductility will have more toughness than a material with low strength and high ductility. So, one way to measure

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toughness is by calculating the area under the stress-strain curve from a tensile test. This value is called material toughness.

Fig: stress-strain curve for different carbon steel.

there are several variables that have a profound influence on the toughness of material, variables are -

- strain rate

→ Temperature

→ Notch effect

fatigue

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A metal may possess satisfactory toughness under static load but may fail under dynamic load. Ductility and toughness decreases as the load or rate of loading increases.

Temperature is the second variable that have major influence on toughness. As temperature is lowered, the ductility and toughness also decreases.

The third variable is notch defect, has due to the distribution of stress. A material may display good toughness under uniaxial stress but when multiaxial stress is produced due to the presence of a notch, the material might not withstand the simultaneous elastic and plastic deformation.

Different types of toughness are

1. Impact toughness
2. Notch "
3. Fracture "

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*** what do you understand by creep?

Ans:

Time depending strain occurring under stress.

The creep strain occurring at a diminishing rate is called primary creep; that occurring at a minimum and almost constant rate, secondary creep; that occurring at an accelerating rate- tertiary creep.

*** How to perform a creep test?

Ans:

To determine creep properties, a material is subjected to prolonged constant tension or compression loading at constant elevated temp. Deformation is recorded at specified time intervals and a creep vs time diagram is plotted.

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slope of curve at any point is steep rate
if failure occurs, it terminates the test and
the time for rupture is recorded ✓
if specimen does not fracture within the test
period, creep recovery may be measured ✓

Next class off

*** what do you understand by column

Ans: (column may be defined as) A structural
member subjected to an axial compressive force
is called a strut and a vertical strut is called
a column

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When a column is subjected to some compressive force then compressive stress induced,

given by -

$$\sigma = \frac{P}{A}$$

where,

P = compressive force

A = cross sectional area of the column

If the force is gradually increased the column may fail by crushing if the ultimate stress exceeded. In case of long column, it mainly fails by buckling. When a long column is subjected to a compressive load, it is under compressive stress and if the load is gradually increased, it will reach a stage when it will start buckling.

The load at which the column just buckled is called buckling load / critical load / crippling load.

And the column is said to have developed an elastic instability.

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For long column the value of buckling load will be less than the crushing load. Moreover, the value of buckling load is low for long column and relatively high for short column.

Discuss briefly Euler column?

Let us consider a column of length L

If it is subjected under compressive load P along the centroidal axis, the bar is bent in the positive y direction. This requires a negative moment and is given by the eqn

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$M = -Py$

$\Rightarrow \frac{d^2y}{dx^2} = -Py$

$\Rightarrow \frac{d^2y}{dx^2} + Py = 0$

This is a second order differential equation for simple harmonic motion. The solution of the equation is given by:

$$y = A \sin \sqrt{\frac{P}{EI}} x + B \cos \sqrt{\frac{P}{EI}} x$$

where A and B are integral constant whose values can be obtained from boundary conditions.

B.c ① At $x=0, y=0$

B.c ② At $x=l, y=0$

This gives $B=0$

The trivial solution of no buckling occurs with $A=0$

If $A \neq 0$, then, $\sin \sqrt{\frac{P}{EI}} l = 0$

$\Rightarrow \sqrt{\frac{P}{EI}} \cdot l = n\pi$

$n \rightarrow$ an integer.

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Feed Force $\sigma = 1$, gives critical load

$P_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2 EI}{L^2}$

But $\sigma = AK\sqrt{P}$ where A is the sectional area and K radius of gyration.

$\therefore P_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2 E (AK)^2}{L^2}$

$\frac{P_{cr}}{A} = \frac{\pi^2 E}{(L/K)^2}$

$\Rightarrow \frac{P_{cr}}{A} = c \frac{\pi^2 E}{(L/K)^2}$

where,

- $c \rightarrow$ End condition constant
- $\frac{L}{K} \rightarrow$ Slenderness ratio

En 4: condition constant for Euler column

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Col ⁿ End condition	c		
	Theoretical value	Conservative value	Recommended value
Fixed free	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{1}{4}$
Rounded - rounded	1	1	1
Fixed rounded	2	1	1.2
Fixed - fixed	4	1	1.2

B.C = Boundary condition.

Prob# A steel rod 5m long and 40 mm diameter is used as a column with one end fixed and the other free. Determine the crippling load by Euler's formula. Assume $E = 200 \text{ GPa}$.

Solⁿ:

Given,

$$l = 5\text{m} = 5 \times 10^3 \text{ mm}$$

$$d = 40 \text{ mm}$$

$$E = 200 \text{ GPa} = 200 \times 10^9 \text{ N-m}^2$$

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we know,

Moment of inertia, $I = \frac{\pi}{64} (d^4)$

Again,

Per = $c \pi r \frac{EI}{l^2}$

$= \frac{1}{4} \pi r^2$

Ann: 2.48 kN

Prob # A hollow alloy tube 4m long with external and internal diameters of 40 mm and 25 mm respectively was found to extend 4.8 mm under a tensile load of 60 kN. Find the buckling load for the tube with both ends fixed.

Ann:

Given,

$l = 4 \text{ m}$

$D = 25 \text{ mm} = 25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}$

$E = 60 \text{ kN}$

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Handwritten notes and diagrams on a page from 'Anwar's Handbook on Materials Engineering and Practices'. The page contains a table with columns labeled A, B, AB, and AB. The text is written in Bengali and discusses topics related to materials engineering, possibly focusing on the properties of different materials or their combinations. There are also some diagrams and a circular stamp that reads 'Data of Final Exam 08.09.09'.

A	B	AB	AB
...

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Spring

A spring is a device in which the material is arranged in such way that it can undergo a considerable change without getting permanently distorted.

Types of spring:

① - Bending spring: A spring which is subjected to only bending load and the resilience is also due to it e.g leaf spring.

② - Torsion spring: A spring which is subjected to twisting moment and the resilience is also due to it. e.g Helical spring.

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Q. Discuss briefly helical springing?

Ans: It is a torsion spring made up of a wire coiled in to a helix. It is again of two types -

- closely coiled helical spring.
- open coiled helical spring.

(a) closely coiled helical spring:

In a closely coiled helical spring wire is coiled so close that the each turn is practically a plane at right angles to the axis of the helix and the wire is subjected to torsion. A closely coiled. Here bending stress is negligible compared to torsional stress.

(b) Open coiled helical spring:

In open helical spring wire is coiled in such a way that there is a large gap betn the two consecutive turns, the spring can take compressive load as well.

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closely coiled spring subjected to an Axial loading?
or, show that stiffness is independent of Axial loading.

Ans:

Consider a closely coiled helical spring subjected to an axial load as shown -

Let,

d = Diameter of the spring wire

R = Mean radius of spring coil

n = No of turns of coil.

C = Modulus of rigidity for the spring material.

W = Axial load on the spring.

τ = Max. shears stress induced in the wire due to twisting

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θ = Angle of twist in the spring wire.

δ = Deflection of the spring due to axial loading.

The load w will cause a twisting moment,

$$T = w \cdot R \quad \text{--- (I)}$$

Again twisting moment,

$$T = \frac{\pi}{16} \times \tau \times d^3 \quad \text{--- (II)}$$

From (I) and (II),

$$w \cdot R = \frac{\pi}{16} \times \tau \times d^3$$

The length of the wire is given by,

$$l = \pi \times 2 \times R$$

We know, $\frac{T}{J} = \frac{C \cdot \theta}{l}$

$$\Rightarrow \theta = \frac{T}{J} \cdot \frac{l}{C}$$

$$= \frac{wR}{\frac{\pi}{32} d^4} \cdot \frac{\pi \times 2 \times \pi R}{C}$$

$$\Rightarrow \theta = \frac{64 w R^2 \pi}{e d^4}$$

∴ Deflection of the spring

$$\delta = R \cdot \theta = \frac{64 w R^3 \pi}{e d^4}$$

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Fixed End Energy stored in the spring, $U = \frac{1}{2} W \cdot \delta$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \frac{64 W^2 R^3 n}{cd^4}$$
$$= \frac{32 W^2 R^3 n}{cd^4}$$

Stiffness of the spring,

$$S = \frac{W}{\delta} = \frac{W \times cd^4}{64 W R^3 n}$$
$$= \frac{cd^4}{64 R^3 n}$$

i.e stiffness is independent of load.

Prob# A closely coiled helical spring is required to carry a load of 150N. If the mean diameter of the coil is 8 times that of the wire, calculate these diameters, consider maximum shear stress as 100 MPa.

Soln;

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Given, the placement of full package ready
Load, $W = 150N$
coil diameter, $D = 8d$
 $d =$ diameter of the wire.
Maximum sheath stress, $T = 100MPa$

We know,
 $T = WR = \frac{\pi}{16} \tau d^3$

$\Rightarrow 150 \times 4d = \frac{\pi}{16} \times 100 \times d^3$

The Parallel $\Rightarrow d = \frac{150 \times 4 \times 16}{\pi \times 100}$

$\therefore d = 5.627 \approx 6mm$ Ans.

$D = 8d = 8 \times 6 = 48mm$ Ans.

Ptc.

The parallel ...

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Prob# A closely coiled helical spring of round steel wire 5 mm diameter having 12 complete coils of 50 mm mean diameter is subjected to an axial load of 100 N. Find the deflection of the spring and maximum shearing stress.
Modulus of rigidity, $c = 80 \text{ GPa}$

Given,

Diameter of spring wire, $d = 5 \text{ mm}$

No of coils, $n = 12$

Diameter of spring, $D = 50 \text{ mm}$

Axial load, $w = 100 \text{ N}$

Modulus of rigidity, $c = 80 \text{ GPa}$

We know,

Deflection of the spring,

$$\delta = \frac{64WR^3n}{cd^4}$$
$$= \frac{64 \times 100 \times (25)^3 \times 12}{80 \times 10^3 \times 5^4}$$
$$= 24 \text{ mm Ans}$$

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Creeling is the placement of full packages ready for weaving. Again, $T = W \cdot R$. All crumple it in the removal of empty. $\frac{\pi}{16} \times \tau \cdot d^3$. Creeling is the place of full packages ready for weaving. $T = 101.9 \text{ MPa}$ Ann. $\tau = 101.9 \text{ MPa}$

Green. Type. \odot

Column $\rightarrow 1 \text{ set}$

Spring $\rightarrow 1 \text{ set}$

Combining $\rightarrow 1 \text{ set}$

Hard, Toughness, creep $\rightarrow 1 \text{ set}$

Mixed $\rightarrow 1 \text{ set}$

Total $\rightarrow 4 \text{ set question}$

Ann. $\rightarrow 3 \text{ set question}$

$W \cdot R = \frac{\pi}{16} \tau d^3$

$\frac{16 W \cdot R}{\pi d^3}$

$= \frac{16 \times 100 \times 25}{\pi \times 53}$

Denary weaving plan which includes the arrangement of warp and weft threads which are interlaced to form fabric. It is the removal of empty packages. \odot Relax

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